

SYNTAGMATIC FEATURES OF NOMINATIVE AND COMMUNICATIVE CLICHÉS.

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Abstract: This article examines clichés as fixed speech units from the perspective of syntagmatic analysis. Clichés are described as ready-made speech formulas that facilitate communication while also conveying semantic, social, and situational information. The author distinguishes between two main types of clichés nominative and communicative and analyzes their structural and functional characteristics. Nominative clichés perform a naming function and operate in a sentence as a single nominative component while preserving their internal structural stability. Communicative clichés, in contrast, function as ready-made speech formulas capable of expressing a complete speech act and serving as independent syntactic units. The paper also discusses the relationship between syntagmatic and paradigmatic relations in language, drawing on Ferdinand de Saussure's ideas.

Keywords: clichés, speech formulas, syntagmatic analysis, nominative clichés, communicative clichés, syntactic structure, speech act, language system

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются клише как устойчивые речевые единицы с точки зрения синтагматического анализа. Подчеркивается, что клише представляют собой готовые формулы речи, которые облегчают коммуникацию и одновременно несут семантическую, социальную и ситуативную информацию. Автор выделяет два основных типа клише — номинативные и коммуникативные — и анализирует их структурные и функциональные особенности. Номинативные клише выполняют функцию называния и выступают в предложении как единый номинативный

компонент, сохраняя внутреннюю структурную устойчивость. Коммуникативные клише, напротив, представляют собой готовые речевые формулы, способные выразить завершённый речевой акт и функционировать как самостоятельные синтаксические единицы. В статье также освещается соотношение синтагматических и парадигматических отношений в языке, опираясь на идеи Ф. де Соссюра.

Ключевые слова: клише, речевые формулы, синтагматический анализ, номинативные клише, коммуникативные клише, синтаксическая структура, речевой акт, языковая система.

Clichés, which are ready-made speech units stably used in the language system, are one of the important means that facilitate communication between people. They embody not only semantic content but also social and situational information. In particular, the inclusion of fixed units expressing speech etiquette among speech formulas demonstrates their close connection with social needs. A speech formula formed within a particular society is typically characterized by its regular occurrence in specific communicative situations. Structurally stable units of this type are classified according to the functions characteristic of a particular level of the language system. On this basis, clichés are studied according to various criteria.

According to the lexical principle, cliché formulas are characterized by their formal separateness and their phrase-like structure. From the syntactic perspective, they may be expressed either in an integrated or in a detached form. At the lexical level, cliché formulas perform a nominative function, while at the syntactic level they fulfill a communicative function.

In linguistics, two main aspects of studying the language system are distinguished, one of which is the syntagmatic aspect. Syntagmatic analysis examines the specific relations between language signs that arise in the process of their sequential combination in speech flow or in a text. In other words, it reflects the sequential connections and combinations within a sentence and appears as “horizontal” relations between language units.

Syntagmatic relations are usually associated with the name of Ferdinand de Saussure. He was one of the first to observe two types of relations that determine the state of the language system at any given moment: syntagmatic and associative (later called paradigmatic) relations. He also proposed the idea that speech is based on linearity, extension, unidirectionality, and sequence. According to Saussure, syntagmatic analysis involves methods for segmenting language sequences and identifying their components, as well as special procedures for determining the influence of one unit on another and their mutual interaction.

In syntagmatic analysis, special attention is paid to the fact that the sequential arrangement of language units in speech is not random but determined by specific regularities and reasons. One of the important stages of analysis consists of identifying the consistent arrangement of units and determining the concrete or abstract positions of elements within a syntagm. At the same time, syntagmatic relations must be studied in conjunction with another important aspect of the language system — paradigmatic relations. Units that can occupy the same syntactic position enter into paradigmatic relations through the possibility of substitution. If syntagmatics shows the horizontal connections of units in speech, paradigmatics reflects their vertical relations in the mind.

From a syntagmatic point of view, clichés have stable patterns of combination. When studying their integration into speech or context, they are divided into nominative clichés and communicative speech clichés, and their degrees of connection are analyzed. Nominative clichés are mainly used in monologic written speech, while communicative clichés are typical of oral dialogic speech, with the exception of certain formulas used at the beginning or end of letters. Accordingly, the two types of speech clichés include units that differ semantically and syntactically. Syntagms are divided into the following types:

- nominal syntagm (SN),
- pronominal syntagm (SPro),
- verbal syntagm (SV),
- adverbial syntagm (SAdv),
- adjectival syntagm (SAdj),

and prepositional syntagm (S_{Prep}).

According to V.

M. Burunskiy, the structural types of nominative clichés correspond to models of phraseological units and stable non-phraseological word combinations and are used in speech for naming figurative expressions. In communicative speech clichés, simple sentence-like structures predominate. This is related to their functional role, as they serve to describe events, situations, or states in a concise and compact form.

Nominative clichés are stable combinations that perform the function of naming objects, phenomena, or states of reality. They mainly fulfill a nominative function and participate in the language system as ready-made naming means. When included in context, nominative clichés do not disrupt the overall semantic coherence of speech. They integrate into sentence structure like ordinary lexical units, are not grammatically isolated, and do not require special marking.

From a syntagmatic perspective, nominative clichés:

1. Function as a single nominative component within a sentence
2. Often follow the noun phrase (SN) model
3. Have a stable internal structure with limited possibilities for free substitution

Examples include:

SN: *coup de foudre*, *point de vue*

SN + Adj: *haute société*

These clichés name objects, phenomena, or abstract notions but do not by themselves perform a complete speech act. Syntagmatically, they function as a single nominative element within a sentence.

For example, *coup de foudre* follows the structural model SN → N + de + N. In the sentence *Ils ont eu un coup de foudre*, the expression functions as an indivisible nominative unit and serves as a direct object. Likewise, *point de vue* (point of view) follows the same model. In *Du point de vue linguistique, ce phénomène est intéressant*, the entire cliché functions as an adverbial modifier forming a single semantic unit within the sentence.

Mise en scène (staging) follows the model $SN \rightarrow N + en + N$. In *La mise en scène de ce film est remarquable*, it functions as the subject. Its internal structure is fixed, but it freely enters external syntagmatic relations.

Communicative clichés are ready-made speech formulas that express a complete thought or speech act. They are often used in communication as social norms. Situation-bound communicative clichés have specific combinatory properties: they can be used both within a sentence and as independent utterances, entering into free relations with other sentences. Nevertheless, they are often grammatically independent from the rest of the text, and their syntagmatic connection with the general flow of speech may be weakened.

From a syntagmatic point of view, communicative clichés:

1. Form structures equivalent or close to a sentence
2. Function as independent communicative units
3. Frequently occur in dialogic speech

Structural models include:

Sentence-like: *Je vous en prie, Merci beaucoup*

Imperative structures: *Excusez-moi, Entrez !*

Modal formulas: *Bien sûr, Pas de problème*

These clichés respond to the whole speech situation and perform specific social functions such as gratitude, apology, agreement, or refusal. They represent ready-made speech formulas expressing a complete speech act and are often equivalent to a sentence.

For instance, *Merci beaucoup* does not have a full sentence structure but functions independently and does not depend on sentence structure. *Je vous en prie* forms the model Pronoun + Verb + Pronoun and functions as an independent predicative unit rather than a sentence component. *Pas de problème*, although structurally a noun phrase, functions communicatively as a full response. *Bien sûr* may function as an independent affirmative speech act or as a modal word within a sentence (*Bien sûr, il viendra*).

Thus, communicative clichés can perform a speech act even outside a broader context.

In conclusion, syntagmatic analysis shows that nominative clichés function as naming units within sentence structure and serve as syntactic components. Communicative clichés, in contrast, function as ready-made speech formulas that represent independent syntactic and pragmatic units. Their main difference lies in their degree of structural independence and their communicative role. Studying clichés from a syntagmatic perspective reveals not only their place in the language system but also their functional load in real speech processes.

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